

GENERAL ISSUES OF DEVELOPMENT AND IMPROVEMENTSPEECH
COMPETENCE OF FUTURE JUNIOR TEACHERSCLASSES

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to general issues of the methodology of developing speech competence of both teachers and primary school students in schools with the Russian language of instruction. The article describes some methods and techniques of teaching the basics of grammar, reading, writing, as well as the development of speech competence of teachers and students at the initial stage of learning. It takes into account the realities (reforms) of recent years in the system of continuing education: focus on modern methods of developmental learning and educational technologies, on organizational forms of different levels of education, on competence-based and communicative approaches to learning, focus on personality-oriented learning that takes into account the interests, abilities and giftedness of modern children.*

Keywords: *school failure, educational activities, reasons for failure, poor academic performance, teacher, family, psychologists, types of failure, the problem of school failure.*

ОБЩИЕ ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ И СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ РЕЧЕВОЙ
КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ МЛАДШИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ КЛАССА

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена общим вопросам методики развития речевой компетентности как учителей, так и учащихся начальных классов в школах с русским языком обучения. В статье описаны некоторые методы и приемы обучения основам грамматики, чтения, письма, а также развития речевой компетентности учителей и учащихся на начальном этапе обучения. Учитываются реалии (реформы) последних лет в системе непрерывного образования: акцент на современных методах развивающего обучения и образовательных технологиях, на организационных формах разных уровней образования, на компетентностном и коммуникативном подходах к обучению, фокусировании на личностно-ориентированное обучение, учитывающее интересы, способности и одаренность современных детей.*

Ключевые слова: *школьная неуспеваемость, учебная деятельность, причины неуспеваемости, неуспеваемость, учитель, семья, психологи, виды неуспеваемости, проблема школьной неуспеваемости.*

One of the main principles and targets of the State National Program for the Development of School Education is a radical improvement of the entire school system of Uzbekistan; formation of educational and material base and educational standards that meet the highest modern requirements.

Primary school is the period when the foundations for personality formation are laid. It should be said that training and education in Uzbekistan is aimed at introducing students to human and national values.

The Russian language in the Republic of Uzbekistan is studied at all three levels of general education, corresponding to the main stages of learning and development of students: 1st stage - primary school (1-4 grades accy), 2nd stage – middle school (grades 5-9), 3rd stage – high school (10-11 grades).

In accordance with this, humanization, democratization, and informatization of education are considered as key positions for school renewal, as factors for accelerating the development of the school - creative search for teachers, the reform of the educational process, its versatility, focus not only on the perception and improvement of social experience, but also on its radical transformation and development, as value priorities that determine the content of learning, are the unconditional value of philological knowledge as the basics of practical literacy, the need for a reasonable balance of effective traditions in the field of education and pedagogical innovation.

From the very first days of studying their native language, the teacher must make students aware of the significant role of the native language in the life of society, i.e. It is necessary to introduce students to language as a means of communication at the very beginning of a systematic course. Knowledge of this function of the language increases children's interest in their native (Russian) language as a learning language, the desire to speak it well in order to better use the language as a means of communication.

A modern teacher and schoolchild, through their teacher, must acquire knowledge about the place and role of the Russian language among other languages of the world and about its functions, which are of great importance not only for the formation of linguistics and worldview, but also to educate students, firstly, respect for other languages and to the native speakers of these languages; secondly, ideas about the equality of all languages with a known difference in the level of development.

An outstanding Uzbek humanist poet, thinker, scientist, artist, statesman of his time, philanthropist and founder of the Uzbek literary language Alisher Navoi in his poetic His simple

and prosaic works raised issues of education and training. He paid great attention to the formation and upbringing of the child, considering him a luminary in the house, bringing joy and happiness to the family. Navoi believed that a child should be given proper education from a young age, in accordance with his age. And we need to start studying science as early as possible. As a supporter of secular education, Navoi attaches great importance to the role and importance of the teacher in society.

“Who was taught one letter
To comprehend the earthly truth.
How will he pay his teacher?

“All earthly riches will not be enough for this,” writes Alisher Navoi, elevating the role of the first teacher.

The teacher must know his subject perfectly and have deep knowledge. Ignorant teachers are a big scourge for schools, Navoi believes.

What knowledge and qualities should a primary school teacher have at the present stage?
This is:

1. Have a rich, colorful, imaginative, beautiful and developed speech, native language.
2. It's good to know the forms, methods and techniques of working to develop and improve not only your own speech, but also the speech of younger schoolchildren. Only through methods and techniques, innovative pedagogical technologies can children develop speech and instill a love for their native language.
3. Constantly work on developing not only your own speech competence, but also the competence of children.

“It is knowledge that ennobles a person, and the transfer of one's knowledge to others brings true happiness.”– wrote the great scientist-encyclopedist of the East Abu Reikhan Biruni.

The formation of any teacher or the preparation of a future specialist is a difficult, lengthy and multifaceted process, which is largely determined by the feelings and experiences that one will receive a young specialist in the first days and months of his teaching activity. Its beginning of success is largely determined by the level of speech and communicative training of the teacher, his communication and speech skills.

Many research scientists, like N.V. Kuzmina, V.A. Kan-Kalik, A.A. Bodalev, A.A. Leontyev, etc. devoted their research works in the field of pedagogy and psychology to the problems of development of speech competence, in general, the communicative activity of the teacher, his speech and communicative possibilities that allow us to define communicative

competence as a set of knowledge and skills in the field of verbal and non-verbal means for adequate perception and reflection you in various situations communication.

The results of the survey on the relevance of the problem under study showed that the students received quite serious professional training and knowledge as psychologists and teachers Czech basics. Several questions of the questionnaire were devoted to identifying the level of communicative training. 35% of those surveyed noted that they do not have sufficient verbal skills, which leads to communication failures. 45% of those surveyed showed a tendency towards an authoritarian style of pedagogical communication. 25% - 30% in a conflict situation choose stressful communication tactics. With all this, more than 50% of graduates admitted that they did not master the techniques of pedagogical communication in the classroom.

Research by some physiologists has proven that 30-40% of neuroses in children are associated with pedagogical communication, since the teacher often resorts to stress tactics (additional utters shouts, reproaches, rudeness, humiliation), which are realized through verbal means of communication.

The native (Russian) language - in the elementary grades is considered the main subject in school, since half of the class time allocated by the curriculum is usually devoted to its study .

K.D. Ushinsky and his followers considered the following to be the goals of the school subject “Native Language”:

- education and development of the student’s personality, instilling respect and love for the native language, formation of linguistic taste, “flair of language”, high culture of speech;
- development of the “gift of speech” – practical development of speech – expression of one’s thoughts and understanding of someone else’s; formation and development (automation through training) of language skills: listening - listening to speech with full understanding, speaking - expressing your thoughts, writing - graphically recording thoughts and so on onets, readings;
- study, analysis of samples – all the best that was created by the masters of words, by the people themselves (literature, folklore);
- based on work on the first four goals – study, research, awareness of the language system in its functioning; the use of a language system to master the norms of literary speech and its expressiveness.

The great Russian writer L.N. Tolstoy also left a big mark on the methods of development of the native (Russian) language. Everyone knows that Leo Tolstoy showed himself as a philosopher, thinker and teacher in his pedagogical activities. As a teacher, he created his own

method of teaching literacy - auditory and compiled the “ABC” in 4 books (1873), which he repeatedly called the main work of his life (13 years of work!).

In his article “Who should learn to write from whom: the peasant children from us or from the peasant children?” he wrote about awakening the spiritual powers of schoolchildren, about their creative takeoff. Leo Tolstoy writes in his works: “I cannot enter the school without experiencing direct physical anxiety, without watching Lomonosov, Pushkin, Glinka, and how to find out who needs what” (ABC. New ABC. M. , 1978.C.8). Modern “pedagogy of non-violence”, creative methods have their roots in the rich storehouse of ideas, plans, and undertakings of this extraordinary person.

Pone language is the greatest teacher who taught children even when there were no books, no schools, no computers, no Internet. And this function has not lost its significance today.

It is necessary to highlight the following main trends that determine the development of native language methods in primary classes over the past ten years:

1. An undoubted and significant increase in scientific knowledge both in the content of the academic subject and in the psychological and linguistic validity of the methodology.
2. The first steps of different levels of education, aimed at the individual capabilities and interests of the student himself.
3. Admission of various linguistic and methodological concepts into the school, a certain pluralism of curricula, textbooks and teaching methods in strict compliance with state educational standards o standard.
4. Attempts to create real opportunities for the school, teacher to choose curriculum, textbooks and methods - methods.
5. General humanitarian direction of school development, methods, humane approach to children; refusal of politicized, biased texts in textbooks on language and literature, in additional materials.
6. A high aesthetic level of all classes, both in language and literature, a high level of cognitive interests and learning motivation; focus on high classical examples, on the creative activity of children, on the connection of language classes with other subjects.

2.The question of the great need for highly professional communication and the level of real speech (communicative) preparedness for it remains relevant today. The formation of professional qualities is included in the tasks of all pedagogical educational institutions, one of which is: developing the ability to use psychologically calling on linguistic means in the process of pedagogical communication.

Today's teacher must constantly work on himself, on improving his speech and overall communicative competence.

Any profession requires the development of certain skills and abilities. The most important skill of a highly qualified specialist is the skill of self-education. Without self-education there can be no talk of developing speech and communicative competence.

Self-education is the main and necessary condition for the professional activity of any teacher. Therefore, the growth of professional skill can also be called finding your own path, finding your own voice.

Constant self-education is one of the particularly important factors in the development and formation of not only professional competence, but also communicative-verbal, linguistic and information skills. this teacher's competencies.

A teacher is a creative profession. A creative teacher-teacher should not work only according to the same lesson plan or scenario from year to year, read the same reports, conduct the same type and monotonous lessons. Work should be interesting and bring pleasure to both yourself and the students.

We must try to be in demand at work. The question arises: In what way? It is no secret to anyone that today many parents, when bringing their child to school, ask to go to class with a specific teacher or class leader.

What should a teacher do to be in demand at work?

This isto constantly keep up with the times, to be always in search of the new, original and unusual.

What types of activities in the process of self-education contribute to increasing professional competence, developing the teacher's speech and communicative competencies?

- Systematic viewing of certain television programs on pedagogical topics;
- Reading periodicals of pedagogical magazines;
- Reading scientific, methodological, pedagogical and artistic literature with its subsequent analysis, conclusions and conclusions;
- Constant familiarization with Internet materials on your subject, pedagogy, psychology and innovative educational technology;
- Participation in training seminars, master classes, scientific and practical conferences, attending open lessons of your colleagues;

Competence of teacher and studentsis expressed in knowledge about language and speech, which is achieved as a result of studying all aspects of the language (its

phonetics, vocabulary, word production, morphology and syntax) and speech (its textual new, style varieties and types of organization of utterance), its both forms oral and written, norms of literary language. All this, learned quite firmly, provides schoolchildren with the conscious use of language in their own speech, a basis for self-control when using language as a means of communication.

Thus, the subject of methods of teaching the Russian language solves the following four important tasks:

- “why study”; – “what to teach”;
- “how to teach”: for this it is important to develop teaching methods and techniques, projects (methodological developments) of lessons based on innovative technologies and their cycles, x manuals for teachers and teaching aids.
- “how to control what you have learned”, i.e. determination of evaluation criteria and control methods.

The goal of the subject teacher “I want to teach” is combined with the goal of the student “I want to learn.” The teacher not only teaches the subject, but also forms a certain level of human relationships.

What is the goal of the theoretical and methodological training of future teachers, on whom the quality of teaching the native (Russian) language depends and, above all, increasing the interest of schoolchildren in studying their native language oh language? This is, first of all:

- equip them with fundamental scientific and methodological knowledge about the process of teaching their native (Russian) language and educating younger schoolchildren using this subject;
- teach you to consciously and purposefully create your own experience of learning the Russian language;
- to develop in future teachers the ability to distinguish what is truly valuable in the experience of others from what is pseudo-new.

The methodology for developing speech competence and teaching the Russian language is unthinkable without methods and techniques of work. It cannot develop, improve without teaching methods and techniques. Every teacher needs to know the types of methods and techniques, their effectiveness and purpose of application, and the methods of their organization.

A modern teacher today needs to work on improving the educational process, using, along with traditional lessons, lessons using active and interactive methods ov and teaching methods and

such non-standard forms of classes as seminars, lesson-conversation, workshops, lesson-auction, thematic “test”

–Vertushka”, etc. in middle and high grades, and in elementary grades–holiday lessons, morning lessons, game lessons, fairy tale lessons, lessons “The path from A to Z...”, lesson – “The magic word”, etc., which require more active independent study of the material, as well as increasing the cognitive activity of schoolchildren.

The development of speech competence is inseparable from the development of thinking and itself contributes to it. It may flow spontaneously, but such speech may turn out to be incorrect and poor. Therefore, today a system for developing students’ speech has been developed and is used in school. It includes the organization of speech situations, the organization of the speech environment, vocabulary work, syntactic exercises, various types of work on texts (connected speech), intonations, correction and perfection absence of speech.

All work on speech development is based on the course of grammar, vocabulary, phonetics, word formation, stylistics, as well as the theory of speech and text, which is not included in the curriculum for students, but is used as the basis for methods of developing students' speech.

3. Thus, a strong command of the Russian language (along with other world languages) is one of the conditions for improving the quality of training of highly qualified specialists, the need for which is growing in modern conditions of accelerating scientific and technological progress (digitalization of society), integration, enrichment of intellectual potential, implementation of large-scale comprehensive social and economic programs, the key to achievements not only in domestic but also in world culture, science, literature and art.

“Today we are witnessing the process of transition from the “school of explanation” to the “school of development”, the transition from the pedagogy of memory to the pedagogy of thinking, from the pedagogy of performance to the pedagogy initiative. Knowledge, abilities and skills cannot be the only pedagogical goal: a modern school must fully develop cognitive capabilities and independent creative activity students and actually, and not in words, educate a developing personality. This means that today everything should be different: the psychological atmosphere of classes, educational content, and teaching methods. Today, students should discover knowledge themselves, and not receive it in a ready-made form.”

All this is contained in the content and structure of the state standard and curriculum for schools with Uzbek, Russian and other languages of instruction.

Every primary school teacher should know at a high level the following goals of teaching methods of the native (Russian) language at the initial stage of education: – development of oral and written speech (communicative, speech and linguistic competencies) of students in unity with the development of their mental activity, awareness of the elements of grammatical structure language, nurturing love for the native language and instilling interest in its knowledge. Based on all these requirements, it should be said that modern schools today need strong, comprehensively educated, creative teachers, professionals in their field. A teacher will only be able to present educational material clearly, clearly and colorfully when he himself has developed speech competence at a high level.

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